

Cloud-Based IoT System for Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring and Control System with Automation

R. Raman, M. Likitha, N. Dinesh, A. Satya Kalyani, A. Jagadeesh

Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Aditya College of Engineering and Technology, Surampalem, Andhra Pradesh, India

To Cite this Article

R. Raman, M. Likitha, N. Dinesh, A. Satya Kalyani & A. Jagadeesh (2025). Cloud-Based IoT System for Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring and Control System with Automation. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(04), 366-372. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15150018>

Article Info

Received: 07 March 2025; Accepted: 30 March 2025; Published: 03 April 2025.

Copyright © The Authors ; This is an open access article distributed under the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

KEYWORDS

Internet of Things (IoT),
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) Sensor,
Node MCU,
Wireless Fidelity (WiFi),
Blynk app.

ABSTRACT

Water Quality management is sought after to be curial significance over the last ten years. Because most of the diseases are propagated due to water contamination, periodic monitoring of water quality should be ensured. Various factors influence the quality of water, i.e., climate change, pollution, population growth etc. In order to prevent serious health problems through contaminated water, water quality management is significant. Internet of Things (IoT) is also among the sustainable methods employed for water quality management. Here in this paper a cloud based IoT system for monitoring and control of water quality in real-time is proposed. Here in this proposed system the water quality is monitored through Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) sensor which provide information regarding organic and inorganic compounds present in the water. In addition, a temperature sensor is employed to display temperature of water. The system gathers data from sensors and uploads sensor values to the cloud via a Wireless Fidelity (WiFi) Module using Node MCU. The System can be operated through mobile via Blynk app. This enables the system to be automated by maintaining the quality of water and the water level minimizing manual intervention

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is a basic requirement of all living organisms and is needed for numerous industrial, agricultural, and residential uses. But with the increased pace of industry, urbanization, and human activities, water pollution has turned into a grave concern, impacting public health and

the environment as well. Existing water quality monitoring systems depend on the manual collection of samples and laboratory analysis, which are time-consuming, expensive, and not efficient for real-time detection of contaminants. Late detection of pollutants can cause extreme health risks, ecosystem

devastation, and non-adherence to regulatory requirements. The growing prevalence of toxic contaminants like heavy metals, pathogens, and chemical pollutants in water bodies has triggered worldwide concern. Such contaminants may come from industrial effluent, agricultural runoff, sewage disposal, and indiscriminate waste disposal. The absence of a proper, automated system for monitoring water quality leads to uncontrolled pollution, and therefore water is not safe for use and consumption. Hence, there is amounting need for a clever, real-time monitoring system with the capability to constantly monitor water quality, give immediate alerts, and automate corrective actions to avert further deterioration. The development in the Internet of Things (IoT) technology has made it possible intelligent water monitoring systems capable of delivering real-time data analysis and remote accessibility. With the integration of IoT-enabled sensors, cloud computing, and automated control mechanisms, a smart water quality monitoring system can provide constant monitoring of key parameters like Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), pH levels, turbidity, temperature, and contamination indicators. The technology facilitates prompt decision-making, enabling authorities and users to take immediate corrective measures. Further, compliance with regulatory bodies like Environmental Protection Agencies and the World Health Organization (WHO) can be ensured using automated reporting and data logging.

a. Objective

The main goal of this project is to develop and deploy a cloud-based IoT system for real-time water quality monitoring and automation of control. The system will ensure continuous monitoring, data analysis, and automated corrective measures to provide safe and clean water for different uses. The system will utilize multiple sensors to gather data on various water quality parameters and utilize cloud technology to store and analyze the data in real-time. The users will be provided with real-time water quality information through a web-based interface and mobile apps, enabling remote monitoring and control. The system will also be integrated with an alert system that informs users and regulatory bodies when contamination levels cross safety limits, enabling them to take immediate action.

The system will also include automatic control devices

like solenoid valves, which can be triggered to shut off water supply upon detection of contamination. This mechanism guarantees that contaminated water is not provided to consumers, avoiding health risks. Additionally, the inclusion of machine learning and AI-powered predictive analytics will allow for early contamination patterns detection, enabling anticipatory interventions before severe pollution takes place. Through mechanized monitoring and control, the system to be recommended lessens the reliance on human intervention, thereby making water management efficient, cost-effective, and reliable.

b. Problem Statement

Clean and safe water is a basic requirement, but contamination from dissolved impurities, temperature fluctuations, and lack of proper monitoring frequently degrades water quality. Conventional water management systems depend on manual intervention and monitoring, resulting in inefficiencies, late responses, and possible health hazards. There is an urgent need for an intelligent, automated system that continuously tracks water quality parameters such as Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), temperature, and water levels, while ensuring real-time intervention to preserve safe and optimum conditions. Real-time monitoring and automatic control mechanisms are lacking, which enhances the risk of ingesting unsafe water and leads to wasteful management of water resources. To meet these needs, a cloud-based IoT system needs to be implemented in order to improve real-time monitoring, automate control decisions, and issue alerts when water quality goes beyond safe parameters. This will enhance water safety, maximize resource use, and minimize manual reliance, making it suitable for residential and commercial use.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Amitesh Kumar (2024) conducted a study on water quality monitoring that integrates IoT sensors with cloud computing to enable real-time data analysis and decision-making. The research emphasizes how IoT sensors can measure key water parameters such as pH, turbidity, and dissolved oxygen. These sensors transmit data to a cloud-based platform, which allows for continuous monitoring and alerts users in case of contamination. The study highlights the advantages of

cloud computing in managing large-scale water monitoring systems by providing remote access, efficient data storage, and predictive analytics. Kumar's work contributes significantly to the field by demonstrating the reliability and efficiency of IoT in ensuring safe water consumption.

Ananth Kumar T. et al. (2024) explored an IoT-based smart water quality monitoring system that utilizes sensor networks to collect real-time water quality data. The system employs microcontrollers and wireless communication to transmit data to a centralized cloud platform for analysis. This study discusses the role of IoT in reducing the need for manual testing while improving accuracy and response time in water quality assessment. The authors also highlight how smart water management systems can be integrated with mobile applications to provide users with instant updates on water conditions. The key contribution of this research is the development of a scalable framework that can be deployed in both urban and rural settings for enhanced water safety and resource management.

Bhardwaj et al. (2022) investigated a smart IoT and machine learning-based framework for water quality assessment. The study integrates artificial intelligence (AI) with IoT to enhance the accuracy of water quality predictions and automate corrective actions. The authors propose a hybrid model where IoT sensors collect data, which is then processed through machine learning algorithms to detect trends and forecast potential contamination events. The research highlights the advantages of combining AI with IoT, including improved decision-making, predictive maintenance, and cost-effectiveness. This study provides valuable insights into how AI-driven automation can optimize water quality management, making it more proactive and efficient.

Wiryasaputra et al. (2024) developed an IoT-based system that continuously monitors potable water quality parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen, total dissolved solids, and temperature. The data is transmitted to a cloud platform for real-time analysis and prediction, facilitating proactive management of water resources.

Ajith Jerome et al. (2020) proposed a smart water quality monitoring system leveraging IoT devices and cloud computing. Their approach emphasizes the use of NodeMCU with built-in Wi-Fi to transmit sensor data to

the cloud, enabling continuous monitoring and analysis. Allen Chafa, et al. (2022) discusses the design of a real-time water quality monitoring and control system using IoT. The system integrates various sensors to measure water quality parameters and employs control mechanisms to maintain water standards, ensuring safe consumption and usage.

Heliyon Journal Article (2024) presents the development of an IoT-based real-time water quality monitoring system tailored for water treatment plants. The system integrates advanced sensor technologies to continuously monitor key water quality parameters, with data transmitted to a centralized monitoring platform utilizing cloud-based storage and analytics.

3. OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SYSTEM

Conventional water quality monitoring systems entail sporadic sampling and laboratory testing, which are extremely inefficient for real-time use. The methods have several drawbacks, such as high costs of operation, lengthy processing time, and vulnerability to human errors. As laboratory testing takes a lot of time for sample collection, transportation, and analysis, the response time to contamination events is delayed. By the time once it is found to be contaminated, it would already have led to health problems, environmental harm, or regulations breaches. Another significant disadvantage of current systems is the absence of real-time monitoring. Because water quality is capable of changing quickly through environmental factors or sudden contamination, intermittent sampling does not reflect current conditions accurately. In addition, traditional monitoring systems lack automated control functionality, and thus it is challenging to promptly take corrective measures. In manufacturing and in municipalities, this can result in massive contamination prior to the authorities being notified of the problem. Also, current monitoring systems lack data storage that is centralized, and therefore it is challenging to monitor historical trends and examine long term water quality patterns. In the absence of a cloud based system, retrieval of data from different locations is made difficult, hindering the capacity of organizations to make sound decisions. Present systems also lack remote access, meaning the personnel must be at the site of the monitoring in order to gather and analyzing data. Such inefficiencies mandate the creation of an advanced

IoT-based solution that provides real-time monitoring, automated control, and remote access to data.

4. PROPOSED APPROACH

The suggested system has been proposed to eliminate the shortfalls of conventional water monitoring methods through the use of IoT-based sensors, cloud computing, and automated response systems. The system comprises smart sensors that regularly monitor major water parameters and send the data to a cloud platform in real-time. This allows for immediate monitoring, remote access, and automatic alerts upon contamination detection. The system is scalable and can be applied to a range of applications, such as municipal water management, industrial water treatment, and irrigation systems for agriculture. Automation of corrective action is one of the main advantages of the suggested system. In case water quality parameters go beyond safety limits, the system is able to initiate solenoid valves to shut off the water supply, preventing dirty water from reaching end users. Also, the system can initiate filtration or purification units to treat contaminated water prior to distribution. This automation eliminates overdependence on manual intervention, making it possible to achieve rapid and efficient responses to contamination incidents.

Another key benefit of this system is its cloud-based design, making it possible to have centralized data storage and analysis. The data obtained from the sensors is transferred to the cloud in real time, where they can be retrieved by authorized persons from anywhere through a web interface or mobile application. This enables improved decision-making capacity through providing historical analysis, trend forecasting, and compliance reporting.

The proposed system also involves an advanced alert system through the use of GSM and IoT-based alerts. Where there is contamination, users receive SMS notifications and mobile notifications, allowing for instant action. In addition, AI-based predictive analytics will assist in identifying possible contamination patterns, enabling preventive action prior to severe pollution. Blockchain technology integration can further ensure data security, with water quality records being tamper-proof and trustworthy.

By adopting this IoT-based solution, industries,

municipalities, and agricultural farms can a great extent enhance water quality management. The system saves operational costs by reducing the requirement for manual monitoring, enhances regulatory compliance through automation data logging, and increases sustainability through ensuring effective utilization of water. The integration of real-time monitoring, automated control, and predictive analytics makes this solution a innovative strategy to water quality management.

Fig.1. Block Diagram of Proposed Work.

The system first gathers the sensors information and sends it to the microcontroller. The Controller process the information and give it to the WiFi module through Node MCU. The data are then stored in the Blynk cloud. Through the Blynk app in mobile the data is analysed by the user. The user send a control information based on the sensors data. When the water level has been reached in the tank the motor is turned off through motor and relay control. The information about the contamination, pH level of the water and temperature of the water is monitored periodically.

A.Data Collection

Data collection involves the collection of sensors data. In the proposed system three sensors are used to namely TDS sensor, temperature sensor and a water level sensor. The TDS sensor used in the proposed system is shown in the Fig. 2. This TDS sensor helps to indicate the total dissolved solid in the water namely, salt, minerals and metals.. It measures the quality of the water through the amount of dissolved solids present in it. The conductivity of the water is directly proportional to the amount of dissolved solids in the water. It calculates the amount of dissolved solids in terms of ppm (mg/l). Thus acts as a good indicator to monitor the water quality

Fig. 2. TDS Sensor.

The second sensor used is the temperature sensor, DS18B20. Fig. 3 shows a one wired digital waterproof temperature sensor used in the proposed system. It measures the temperature of the water and sends it information to the microcontroller.

Fig. 3. Temperature Sensor

The third sensor used in the proposed system is the water level sensor shown in Fig. 4. This sensor consist of about ten exposed copper trace out of which five are termed as power trace and the remaining five are termed as sense trace.

Fig. 4. Water level Sensor

These two traces are not connected with each other. When they are immersed in water the power trace and the sense trace gets bridged forming a variable resistor, whose resistance is varied based on the amount of water exposed to it. Its resistance is inversely proportional to the amount of water exposed. Thereby measuring the level of the water by its resistance value given to the microcontroller.

B. Data Processing

The data is processed using Arduino UNO which a microcontroller board based on ATmega328P

microcontroller is shown in Fig.5. The in the Arduino, programming was done through Integrated Development Environment (IDE) base on embedded C. WiFi module ESP8266 enables a connection between the hardware and software part of the system. Once the sensor data's are received the microcontroller analyses the data and first displays the TDS values and temperature of the water in the LCD display. Then through Blynk app instalred in android mobile the output is seen by the end user through the WiFi connectivity.

Fig. 5. Arduino UNO

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The project titled "Cloud-Based IoT System for Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring and Control System Automation" focuses on developing an automated system for continuous water quality assessment using IoT. Traditional water monitoring methods are slow, expensive, and ineffective for real-time detection, leading to potential health hazards. To address this, the proposed system integrates IoT-enabled sensors such as TDS sensors for water purity, temperature sensors, ultrasonic sensors, and water level monitors. These sensors provide real-time data, which is transmitted to a cloud platform for storage, analysis, and remote access. Additionally, the system includes automated responses, such as solenoid valves that shut off contaminated water and water pumps that refill tanks when necessary. An alert system using IoT and GSM technology ensures that users receive instant notifications if water quality parameters exceed safe thresholds. The system is programmed using the Arduino IDE, and the Blynk app is used for cloud integration. Compared to traditional methods, this IoT-based solution is more efficient, cost-effective, and allows remote monitoring and automated corrective

actions. The project incorporates NodeMCU ESP8266, Arduino, a relay module, power supply circuits, and multiple sensors for real-time operation. A literature survey was conducted to analyze previous research on IoT-based water monitoring systems, helping refine the design and implementation. The project results demonstrate that the system effectively detects water quality changes and takes corrective actions automatically. This solution has significant applications in residential areas, industries, agriculture, and municipal water supply systems. The project was successfully developed by four students under the guidance of a professor at Aditya College of Engineering and Technology, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering. Future enhancements may include AI integration for predictive analysis and expansion to larger water management systems, ensuring safer and more sustainable water usage.

Fig.8. Smart Aqua Guard IoT

Fig.9. Automation system

Fig.6. Smart Aqua Guard IoT

Fig.7. Smart Aqua Guard IoT

6. CONCLUSION

The automation-enabled IoT-based water level and quality monitoring system provides a strong solution for real-time water management with the combination of sophisticated sensors, IoT technology, and automated controls. This system keeps monitoring critical parameters of water such as water levels, pH, turbidity, and temperature in real time, making it possible to immediately identify anomalies and take prompt action against possible problems. Automation minimizes the requirement for manual intervention. intervention and data-driven decision-making, the system increases operational efficiency, lowers costs, and encourages sustainable water use. In the end, it offers a scalable and effective solution for enhancing water quality and resource management across different sectors, leading to environmental sustainability as well as public safety.

7. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

Future research on the Smart IoT-based Water Quality and Level Monitoring System with Automation may include infusing AI and machine learning with predictive analysis so that the system is capable of

predicting water quality problems as well as trends in water level. In the future, greater advances in sensors and power-effective IoT devices will also provide more precision as well as long-term sustainability, especially for geographically isolated zones. Data analysis through the cloud would enhance scalability and real-time decision-making, whereas the system may be integrated with smart city infrastructure for improved coordination in urban management. Additional automation, including integrating automated water treatment processes, and the application of blockchain for data security and transparency, would further improve the efficiency and reliability of the system in managing water resources.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amitesh Kumar. "A Study on Water Quality Monitoring using IoT Sensors and Cloud Computing." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, February 2024, pp. g385–g387. IJ Publication. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10901962.
- [2] Ananth Kumar T., Ramapraba J., Kanimozhi P., and Ajagbe S. A. "IoT Based Smart Water Quality Monitoring System." *IET Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2023, issue 44, 27 February 2024. The Institution of Engineering and Technology. DOI: 10.1049/icp.2024.0944.
- [3] Bhardwaj A., Dagar V., Khan M. O., Aggarwal A., Alvarado R., Kumar M., Irfan M., and Proshad R. "Smart IoT and Machine Learning-Based Framework for Water Quality Assessment and Device Component Monitoring." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International*, vol. 29, no. 30, June 2022, pp. 46037. Springer-Verlag. DOI: 10.1007/s11356-022-19782-y.
- [4] Wiryasaputra, R., Huang, C.-Y., Lin, Y.-J., & Yang, C.-T. (2024). An IoT Real-Time Potable Water Quality Monitoring and Prediction Model Based on Cloud Computing Architecture. *Sensors*, 24(4), 1180.
- [5] Ajith Jerome, B., Manimegalai, R., & Ilayaraja, V. (2020). An IoT Based Smart Water Quality Monitoring System using Cloud. In *Proceedings of the 2020 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Engineering (ic-ETITE)*, Vellore, India.
- [6] Allen Chafa, Gibson Chirinda, Stephen Matope, "Design of a Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring and Control System Using Internet of Things (IoT)" 2022, DOI:10.1080/23311916.2022.2143054.
- [7] Heliyon Journal Article (2024). IoT Based Real-Time Water Quality Monitoring System in Water Treatment Plants (WTPs).